

Exploration of the Path to Promote the Sustainable Development of Zhoushan Island in the Context of the ‘Two Mountains’ Theory

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Abstract – The ‘Two Mountains’ theory is the basic core of Xi Jinping's thought on ecological civilisation, which profoundly interprets the basic laws of economic and social development, answers the major question of ‘what is green development and how to achieve high-quality green development’, and guides the way forward for the sustainable development of island areas. This paper takes Zhoushan Island as an example. This paper takes Zhoushan Island as an example, discusses the practical path and effect of the ‘two mountains’ theory to promote the construction of islands, and builds the institutional mechanism of benign interaction between the ‘two mountains’. Problems are found in Zhoushan, and on this basis, an optimisation path is proposed, including cultivating talents and improving the development mode of the island, hoping to provide experience for the sustainable development of Zhoushan island.

Keywords: ‘Two Mountains’ Theory; Sustainable Development; Practical Path; Zhousha Island

Introduction

The report of the Twentieth Party Congress states: ‘Promote green development and harmonious coexistence between human beings and nature. We must firmly establish and practice the concept that green water and green mountains are golden silver mountains, and plan for development at a high level of harmony between human beings and nature.’ Under the leadership of the ‘two mountains’ theory, Zhejiang Province has successfully transformed from high-speed economic GDP to high-quality green GDP, embarked on the ecological protection and green development complementary to the ‘two mountains’ sustainable development path, and become the first ecological civilisation in the country. province [1]. This paper takes Zhoushan island as an example, discusses the ‘two mountains’ theory to promote the construction of the island practice path and effect, the process of carrying out green governance, eco-tourism sustainable development, etc., adhere to the ecological priority, green development, broaden the ‘two mountains’ transformation path, and strive to explore the characteristics of the rich Zhoushan island, the ‘two mountains’ sustainable development path. Zhoushan island characteristics of the sustainable development of the island road.

1. The ‘two mountains’ theory to promote the value of island construction embodiment

1.1 Help to stimulate the ecological production of the countryside

The so-called industrial ecology, that is, in the means of production and input factors in the whole process of ecological transformation, focusing on economic and social benefits at the same time, the realization of ecological benefits; the so-called ecological industrialisation, that is, in accordance with the laws of industrial development, the ecological wealth into economic wealth, the ‘green mountains’ into the ‘silver mountains’, and continue to enhance ecological assets and value-added potential [2]. Practice has proved that the ‘two mountains’ theory provides a powerful ideological impetus and practical guide for rural revitalisation. Accelerating the organic integration of ecological restoration and rural development, and achieving the organic unity of the green economy, innovative development and ecological civilisation construction can better achieve rural revitalisation. We should take ecology as the foundation, take the countryside as the carrier, take the people as the centre, follow the law of rural development, focus on enhancing the people's sense of access, happiness and security, and achieve comprehensive rural revitalisation.

1.2 In favour of promoting the sustainable development of islands and their economies

General Secretary Xi Jinping stressed in the National Ecological Environmental Protection Conference that ‘the strictest system to protect the ecological environment, in order to achieve the modernisation and greening of man and nature, man and society in harmonious development’ [3]. With the ‘two mountains theory’ as the lead, in-depth practice of the green development concept, take the ecological protection as the main body, green development as the theme of high-quality development road, not only in line with the actual needs of rural development, but also can minimise environmental damage and waste of resources. The key to island development is the healthy development of the island economy, the core of which is focused industrial development, i.e., tourism and fisheries as the mainstay, supplemented by offshore financial services, industry and the construction of free trade zones, which also include options for an ecological economy.

Practice Status

Zhoushan Island, with the ‘two mountains’ theory as a guide, to ecological civilization construction as a hand, to green development as the goal, out of a Zhoushan characteristics of ecological civilization construction road, for the national marine ecological civilization construction provides Zhoushan samples. Zhoushan City Bureau of Ecology and Environment to Xi Jinping ecological civilisation thought as a guide, and earnestly practice the important concept of ‘green water and green mountains is the golden silver mountain’ continue to strengthen marine ecological environmental protection, and promote the construction of marine ecological civilisation, and has achieved remarkable results.

2.1 Enhance green awareness and promote the construction of ecological civilisation on the islands

2.1.1 Insist on harmony between people and the sea, and pay attention to people's well-being.

Zhoushan Island will take the point to lead the surface, in the whole region to carry out Zhoushan Island ecological civilization to create a model city creation and ‘no waste city’ key project construction, in the economic system and civilized society to create a balance between

the governance and supervision of the situation, and actively open up the marine garden city ecological space, to ‘wisdom ‘management instead of’ governance “management, build” environmental monitoring + early warning prevention and control system “in the province to take the lead in the realization of” a matter of environmental credit repair It is the first in the province to realise ‘environmental credit repair in one case’, and is the first in the province to realise ‘online full-process handling’^[4]. Shengsi, Putuo, Daishan successively won the National Ecological Civilisation Construction Demonstration County, created the province's first regional tourism demonstration area^[5].

2.1.2 Carry forward the culture of fishing and ploughing and promote the prosperity of marine culture

Zhoushan Sea Island is actively carrying out on-site performance activities of marine non-heritage projects and humanistic experience projects of fishery and ploughing inheritance in ancient fishing villages in the East China Sea, so as to improve public awareness and participation in marine non-heritage projects, and to let more people understand and participate in the protection and inheritance of marine non-heritage projects. The Zhoushan municipal government has actively organised various marine cultural activities, such as the Zhoushan Island Marine Music Festival, the Zhoushan Island Marine Literature Collection, and the Ocean Festival Fishermen's Festival. The holding of these activities not only enriches the cultural life of Zhoushan people, but also broadly mobilises the love and inheritance of marine culture on Zhoushan Island.

2.1.3 Discovering the cultural qualities of the islands and enhancing the sense of common identity

In order to reflect its island cultural qualities and tell the story of marine culture of Zhoushan Island, a number of island literature rich in regional characteristics of Zhoushan Island has emerged, and academic papers such as ‘Marine Culture and Island Civilisation’, ‘Study on Protection and Development Countermeasures of Zhoushan Marine Cultural Resources’, ‘Study on the Inheritance and Development of Dinghai's Classical Music’, ‘Excavation and Study of Famous Tombs of Zhou's Tang Dynasty in Zhoushan’ and so on, have been published. These results provide theoretical support and practical support for the development of Dinghai island tourism culture.

2.2 Carry out green governance to protect the ecological environment of the islands

2.2.1 Improving marine protection policies

Zhoushan City has formulated a scientific and reasonable fishing plan to ensure the sustainable use of resources. At the same time, government departments have also formulated strict fishing laws, regulations and rules to protect the survival and reproduction capacity of marine biological resources, and the whole sea area has completed the marine biodiversity survey and assessment, which is the first time to comprehensively map out the marine biology of the whole sea area of Zhoushan Sea Island, and provides a basis for marine biodiversity and ecological protection and management. In Zhoushan Island, the relationship between marine ecological protection and fishery development has become increasingly close. Through the implementation of ecological fisheries, green aquaculture and other measures to

reduce fishery pollution and ecological carrying pressure, to achieve a win-win situation between ecological protection and fishery development. At the same time, Zhoushan Sea Island also actively promotes marine ecological protection and management, strengthens marine environmental monitoring and early warning, and establishes a sound system of marine ecological protection laws and regulations, which provides a strong legal guarantee for marine ecological protection and fishery development.

2.2.2 Structure the system of governing pollution

Focus on the living environment of residents, promote the integration of green recycling economy and emerging industries, and achieve the unity of economic development and ecological protection. 2024 Zhoushan Sea Island City carried out 83 sewage projects with a total investment of nearly 1.2 billion yuan, focusing on the key points of water environmental protection, accelerating the construction of environmental infrastructure, integrating the work of flood prevention, drainage and water conservation and water supply, making up for the shortcomings and weaknesses of water treatment, and creating a model benchmark for water treatment to add colour to the construction of beautiful sea islands. Sea Island construction to add glory. 2025, Zhoushan Sea Island once again proposed to systematic governance to promote the organic unity of environmental protection and development, and the implementation of 95 ecosystem protection and restoration projects, with a total investment of up to 1.5 billion yuan. Attacking the Qiguo Coast Polar Flying Beach Restoration and Cultural Landscape Enhancement Project, Wuzhuang Haicheng Coastal Zone Environmental Comprehensive Improvement Project, and South Hui Tsui Wetland Landscape Restoration Project at the mouth of the Yangtze River.

2.2.3 Implementation of comprehensive remediation actions

Zhoushan Island City has adopted engineering technologies such as beach restoration and maintenance, coastal vegetation restoration and planting, and coastal ecological corridor construction to improve the level of remediation and restoration of coastal ecological functions. Putuo District 'Blue Bay' remediation project was selected as one of the 16 typical cases of Zhejiang natural resources system to practice the concept of 'two mountains', 'becoming another major achievement of the marine ecological compensation mechanism in Zhejiang practice[6]. Zhoushan City has also invested a large amount of money to implement the strategy of science and technology to develop fisheries, promote energy efficient aquaculture technology and equipment, and improve the productivity and efficiency of the aquaculture industry. Zhoushan City has realised the sustainable development of marine fisheries through many initiatives and made positive contributions to marine ecological environmental protection. Zhoushan Sea Island has made remarkable achievements in marine ecological environmental protection. The municipal party committee and the municipal government attach great importance to the prevention and control of marine pollution, and have continuously strengthened the management of pollution sources such as aquaculture and diesel engine emissions from ships, and have jointly investigated and handled a number of cases of marine pollution in cooperation with public security, marine and other departments, which has formed a favourable environmental regulatory atmosphere. At the same time, Zhoushan Island City has continued to improve the regular regulatory mechanism for marine rubbish and strengthened the collection, cleaning and disposal of rubbish at sea and on shore, with good results.

Main Problems

3.1 Fewer talents stay in Zhoushan, more scarce talent resources

For a long time, Zhoushan Island has faced the development dilemma of talent shortage. Only a few local talents return to Zhoushan Island to work, and most of them stay in the inland cities. Zhoushan Island mainland island project was completed, especially in recent years with the national strategic initiatives to promote the implementation and construction of major projects, the new area of talent recruitment efforts continue to increase, the introduction of talent has improved, but overall the shortage of talent is still a constraint on the development of Zhoushan Island short board ^[7]. First, the release of large strategies and projects is still in the ‘window period’. At present, the new area development and construction of large projects landing a lot, but most of the projects are still in the start-up phase. Second, to attract high-end talent, international talent conditions and atmosphere is insufficient. Subject to location conditions, economic volume, industrial base and other factors, Zhoushan Island, various types of parks and development zones, universities and research institutes and scientific and technological innovation platform is relatively small, the talent platform level is also relatively low, for the large-scale introduction of high-quality and highly skilled personnel there is still a certain degree of difficulty.

3.2 Infrastructure and public service level still needs to be upgraded.

In the peak season of tourism, a large number of tourists from all over the country flocked to Zhoushan Island, resulting in congestion at the pier and a shortage of boats, while the safety issue is also more prominent, the tourism order, service quality, market environment and other aspects need to be improved ^[8]. Firstly, the contradiction between the supply side and demand side of tourism is more prominent, with Putuo Mountain sightseeing and Buddhist tourism as the main focus, a single tourism and leisure project, and the tourism service facilities are not compatible with the needs of tourists; secondly, the land-island traffic is still a problem, and most of the islands have not yet realised the land-island connectivity between the islands. Although many small islands have passenger routes, they are unable to overcome bad weather and have limited vessel carrying capacity; thirdly, with the protection of tourism resources and increased ecological constraints, the capacity of tourists at key scenic spots with special characteristics is limited, which will also affect and constrain the further development of the tourism industry.

3.3 Ecological environmental protection measures still need to be improved

From the point of view of geographic location, Zhoushan Island is the continental shelf extension of the islands, although relatively independent ecosystem, but its ecosystem is extremely fragile, once damaged, it is difficult to recover ^[9]. Zhoushan Island is located in the East China Sea waters, is the Yangtze River, Qiantang River, Yongjiang River outlet, industrialisation along the river basin, urbanisation into the sea of ‘sludge and dirty water’ has caused serious pollution of seawater. In addition, in the development of tourism at the same time the environmental damage to the island's shortcomings are increasingly visible. The massive increase in the number of tourists has accelerated the depletion of the island's natural resources, as well as causing varying degrees of pollution.

Optimisation Path

4.1 Invest in cultivating local talents

First of all, we should follow the objective law of regional development and talent cultivation. According to the actual situation of Zhoushan Island New Area development, analysis and prediction of the total amount of talent demand, according to the need to formulate the talent work of medium- and long-term planning, annual plans and implementation programmes. Second, to make a breakthrough in the innovation of talent work system and mechanism. Establish and improve the flexible sharing of talent mechanism. Third, in the introduction of talent, training, selection, use, etc., to adhere to the ‘integrity-based, moral and talent’ principle, establish and improve the integrity of the talent file, the integrity of the talent dynamic management. Finally, to retain talent. Improve the infrastructure, improve the level of public services, enhance the ecological environment, create entrepreneurship and innovation, livable and workable quality of life island, and further create a favourable atmosphere for attracting and cultivating talents^[10].

4.2 Improve the sustainable island development model

Through the integration of urban and rural areas and the expansion of urban functions, optimise the spatial structure of the islands and form a development model of ‘stringing pearls into chains’^[11]. Based on the beautiful islands, create a cluster development area across small islands and promote the development of rural tourism industry on the islands. To combine the characteristics of planning small island tourism creative industry, make full use of the core elements of the island, Guanyin and ecology, planning a number of comprehensive, thematic leisure and holiday projects. Zhoushan has made remarkable progress in terms of transport, with the Yongzhou-Zhou High Speed Railway commencing construction, and the East-West Expressway and Esplanade having been completed, all of which have had a positive impact on Zhoushan's tourism. However, the construction of the parking system and the improvement of public transport still need to be further upgraded.

4.3 Promoting the concept of ecotourism

In the process of promoting ecotourism, we should start from the perspective of development and operation, and strengthen the publicity of ecological and environmental protection consciousness of tourists. At the same time, we should establish a perfect ecotourism management system and mechanism to provide a guarantee for the sustainable development of ecotourism. Under the guidance of the ‘two mountains’ theory, the inheritance of marine culture has been redefined, and plays a ‘frontier position’ in the construction of contemporary ecological civilisation^[12]. In addition, we need to strengthen the supervision of ecotourism and establish a sound ecotourism supervision system to ensure the healthy development of ecotourism. At the same time, we also need to strengthen the training of ecotourism practitioners to improve their professional quality and service level to meet the needs of consumers.

Conclusion

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The practical exploration of the ‘two mountains’ concept has a long way to go. Zhoushan Islands to ecological prosperity to help industrial prosperity, environmental remediation to help the island rural governance, ecological civilisation to revitalize the island culture, to achieve social benefits, ecological benefits and economic benefits steadily improved, in the future, Zhoushan Islands will continue to be guided by the theory of the ‘two mountains’, to walk out of a man and nature integration of prosperity and coexistence of the green and gold way, and continue to promote the construction of sustainable development of the island. The construction of sustainable development islands.

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References

- [1] Shen Manhong. (2016) . The practical study of the important thought of“Two mountains” in Zhejiang. *Observation and thinking* (12) , 23-30.
- [2] Jiang Changyun & Yang Yi. (2024) . We will continue to promote the building of a strong agricultural country through chinese-style modernization. *Economic Horizon* (09) , 16-24. doi:10.16528/j.cnki.22-1054/f.202409016.
- [3] Qi Ji. (2019) . The value realization and cultural enlightenment of“Two mountains” theory in rural revitalization. *Journal of the Shandong University (philosophy and social sciences)* (05) , 145-155.
- [4] Hu Yongjun, Wu Jian & Hu Ruishan. (2019) . The inherent logic and development path of the theory of“Two mountains” in the construction of ecological civilization. *Chinese engineering science* (05) , 151-158.
- [5] Yan Li. (2023) . Some thoughts on the construction of island garden under the guidance of the “Two Mountains” theory -- taking Ningbo as an example. and the times (urban edition)(03) , 55-57.
- [6] Li Juan. (2019) . Review and reflection on the 40-year construction of China's ecological civilization system. *Social Sciences in Chinese universities* (02) , 33-42 + 158.
- [7] Yu Zheqian. (September 10,2024) . Zhoushan has created a blue-green symphony of marine ecological civilization. *Zhoushan daily*, 008.doi:10.38335/n.cnki.nzsbr.2024.001237.
- [8] Gao Rong. (2024-07-04) . Take up the responsibility of protecting Zhoushan and build up the ecological foundation. *Zhoushan daily*, 001. doi:10.38335/n.cnki.nzsbr.2024.000837.
- [9] New Urban Management Committee Party Committee Theory Study Center Group.(2024-07-12) . To promote the development of new Zhoushan as the core of a modern maritime city. *Zhoushan daily*, 003.doi:10.38335/n.cnki.nzsbr.2024.000886.
- [10] Lu Qingyun & Qian Cai. (2024) . Reflections on the path of rendering the “Background” of modern urban construction -- a case study of modern marine city construction in Zhoushan. *Research on industrial innovation* (06) , 49-51.
- [11] Xu Zhujun, Wu Ziming, and Ji Fengmei. "Zhoushan: striding towards a first-class and strong port", *Zhoushan daily*, August 17,2021, new area discovery.doi:10.38335/n.cnki.nzsbr.2021.001504.
- [12] Xie Jia, Liu Xin and Chen Wanjie. (2024-08-31) . Putuo District, Zhoushan: introduce a training plan to strengthen the talent team. *People's daily*, 003. doi:10.28651/n.cnki.nrmga.2024.004710.